

How GitOps solves Experiment Configuration Documentation

Moritz Kröger

Agenda

- 1 Who am I**
- 2 Motivation Microservices**
- 3 Infrastructure as Code**
- 4 GitOps for scientific experiments**
- 5 Summary**

Who am I?

Chair:

LLT RWTH Aachen (since 2018)

Graduation:

M.Sc Engineering and Economics

Laserprocess:

- Microstructuring
- Metal 3D Printing

Personal Research Topic:

- Data infrastructure for manufacturing
- Cloud based manufacturing systems
- Integration of Data science into Laser manufacturing

Internet of Production 2019 - 2025

- Cluster of Excellence „Internet of Production“
- Funding ~ 50 Mio €
- 35 institutes involved in Aachen
- 200 involved scientists
- The only excellence cluster for manufacturing in Germany

Vision of the Internet of Production – Digital Shadows

Industry Partners

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Motivation – Ultra short pulse manufacturing

Source: Fraunhofer ILT

Ultrashort Pulse Ablation Machine Setup

Motivation

Due to increasing sensor acquisition rates we are already handling distributed computer systems!

Let's try microservices!

General Idea

Microservice-based Control & Measurement System

- Monolith
A single executable software application whose modules rely on sharing the resources of the same computer. [1]
- Microservice
A minimal independent process interacting via messages. [1]
- Messaging delay ~ milliseconds → No “real” time control

[1]: Microservices: yesterday, today, and tomorrow (Dragoni, 2016)

[2]: Microservices (Martin Fowler, 2014)

Objectives

- **Standardization** of hardware & process logic
- **Connectivity**: Hardware, Sensors **AND** data analysis in **ONE** system
- **Flexibility & Expandability**
- **Short development cycles**
- **Open Source**
- **Multi Language Support**
- **Possibility Realtime Synchronization across Services**

→ **Modular machine** → **Modular software**

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Managing Microservices - Docker

- Image based deployment of software
- Runs everywhere
- Automated deployment possible
- **Allows hardware control**

Managing Microservices - Kubernetes in a nutshell

kubernetes

- Cluster/Server Manager
- Docker orchestration tool
- Offspring of Google's Borg
- ~45.000 Developers
- Completely open source

Kubernetes in a nutshell

ArgoCD for Hardware Deployment

Argo Demo

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What is a Deployment?

What is a Deployment?

Example 1:

What is a Deployment?

Example 2:

ArgoCD for Hardware Deployment

Solving scientific reproducibility

Versuchsnummer	Material	Laserleistung [W]	RepRate in kHz	Framerate Camera	HDR Enabled
1	In718	220	80	400	no
2	In718	240	120	400	no
3	In718	260	80	400	no

Versuchsnummer	Material	Machine Config Git Commit
1	In718	e3e6899
2	In718	8cf8463b
3	In718	34caa8ac

- No Human Documentation needed
- Documents all Parameters automatically
- Reroll possible
- Easy to retrieve automatically

Argo Demo

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Summary

- Microservices for manufacturing systems
- Use of a Centralized Management System (Kubernetes) for Sensors, Actuators, Databases and Analytics
- Automatic generation of documentation through Git Commits
- Change in Git Automatically gets deployed via Argo
- Human errors are avoided through automation

Questions?

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Backup: New Agenda
